

Impacts of Blended Learning on Students' Engagement in Classroom Oral Activities

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to investigate the effects of blended learning on student engagement in oral activities in class. The study participants were first year Moral education students at Hawassa College of Teacher Education in Ethiopia. The researchers used a quasi-experimental design by purposively selecting two intact groups. Data were collected using a pre-intervention survey as a pretest, a post-intervention survey as a posttest and classroom observations. The researchers analyzed the data using inferential and descriptive statistics in SPSS version 27, and a t-test was used to compare the mean differences between the two groups. In addition, the effect size was calculated to determine the magnitude of the intervention and a multiple regression analysis was conducted to determine which feature of blended learning contributed most to increasing students' engagement in oral activities in class. Finally, the results showed that the participants in the experimental group significantly increased their engagement in classroom oral activities and showed a positive attitude towards blended learning. Most of the features of blended learning, with the exception of assessment and face-to-face instruction, contributed to the increase in student engagement. Therefore, English teachers should use blended learning, combining conventional and digital teaching methods to increase student engagement in the classroom.

Keywords: Blended learning; Students' engagement; Students' attitude; face-to-face learning

INTRODUCTION

In this digital era, the educational landscape has changed significantly through the integration of digital technology and innovative teaching methods. One such approach that has gained prominence is blended learning, in which face-to-face teaching methods are combined with online learning (Garrison & Kanuka, 2004a). This model allows for a more personalized and flexible learning experience as students can access course materials and activities both in the classroom and online. As noted by (Bonk & Graham, 2012), blended learning provide students with more control over learning by utilizing technology, such as learning management systems, video conferencing, and online assessments, to complement classroom activities.

Thus, it is integrated instruction that increases flexibility by enabling personalized learning via technology integration, which yields improved engagement. Engagement in classroom activities, particularly oral activities, plays a pivotal role in developing students' communication skills, critical thinking, and overall academic performance (Hung, 2015). Oral activities, such as discussions, presentations, and peer interactions, are essential for fostering a dynamic learning environment. However, the advent of blended learning has

prompted educators to reconsider how these activities are structured and delivered (Lazorenko, 2021).

Nevertheless, creating an engaging and interactive classroom setting for oral activities can be challenging, particularly in large classes with limited instructional time. Face-to-face language classrooms frequently struggle to allocate adequate time and resources for students to actively participate in extended speaking practices (Aliakbari & Jamalvandi, 2010 and Bahrani & Soltani, 2012). Insufficient opportunities for individual feedback and personalized guidance can also hinder students' willingness to participate and share their ideas verbally (Nunan, 2015). The use of blended learning approaches may offer a promising solution to address these challenges and enhance student engagement in classroom oral activities. In addition, blended learning environments can provide increased exposure to the target language, more opportunities for self-paced practice and review, and personalized feedback from instructors and peers ((Banditvilai, 2016 and Dziuban et al., 2018). By examining the interplay between online resources and in-person interactions, the study seeks to identify how this instructional model influences students' participation in classroom oral activities. Understanding these dynamics is essential for educators aiming to enhance learning outcomes and prepare students for the active learning. Therefore, the researchers have formulated the following research questions:

1. What is the level of student engagement in oral activities in blended learning environments compared to conventional learning settings?
2. What specific feature of blended learning most significantly impact students' engagement in classroom oral activities?
3. How do students perceive the usefulness of blended learning in improving their engagement in classroom oral activities?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Today's rapidly developing information and communication technology (ICT) has changed the educational landscape and in particular the field of language teaching. In this context, this review examines the existing literature on the impact of blended learning on student engagement in oral activities in the classroom, highlighting different aspects of student engagement in relation to language learning. Blended learning is characterized as an educational approach that integrates face-to-face teaching with online components, allowing for a flexible and personalized learning experience (Hockly, 2018). Blended learning not only facilitates content delivery but also enhances student engagement through interactive and collaborative learning environments (Lazorenko, 2021). This integration fosters deeper learning experiences, particularly in developing oral communication skills.

Engagement in oral activities is vital for developing communication abilities, critical thinking, and collaborative skills (Kuh, 2009). Blended learning environments offer students the opportunity to participate in discussions and presentations, which is essential for enhancing oral engagement. The use of technology in blended learning allows for varied instructional methods that cater to different learning styles, promoting greater participation in oral activities (Ehsanifard et al., 2020). Additionally, the online and digital components of blended learning, such as interactive multimedia, virtual discussions, and collaborative projects, can create a more stimulating and engaging learning experience for students, potentially fostering their motivation and participation in oral classroom activities (Sharma & Barrett, 2008). Developing students' active classroom engagement is a critical component of language learning as it allows them to improve their oral communication skills with the target language and participate in authentic interactions.

Student engagement in the classroom refers to the level of active participation, interest and commitment they show during classroom activities and lessons. Classroom engagement is a

multifaceted construct that encompasses cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and social dimensions (Pentaraki & Burkholder, 2017). Cognitive engagement involves mental and strategic thinking that students apply to their learning tasks. This includes their willingness to exert the necessary cognitive resources to comprehend, analyze, and synthesize information (Eryilmaz & Altinsoy, 2021). Emotional engagement refers to students' affective reactions and attitudes towards their learning experiences (Hewson, 2018). This includes students' level of interest, enthusiasm, and enjoyment in classroom activities. Behavioral engagement encompasses observable actions and participation of students in the classroom, such as attentiveness, persistence, and active involvement in discussions and learning tasks (Zhou et al., 2024). Social engagement refers to the extent to which students interact and collaborate with their peers and teachers in the classroom setting (Mihai et al., 2022). Social engagement fosters a sense of community in the classroom and can enhance learning through the exchange of ideas and development of social skills (Sulis, 2022). Fostering high levels of classroom engagement is crucial to promoting student learning, academic achievement, and overall educational success.

Several studies revealed that blended learning has a positive impact on student engagement and academic outcomes (Ehsanifard et al., 2020). Regardless of the potential benefits of blended learning in improving learners' engagement in oral activities, empirical research on this topic remains limited. While some studies have explored the general effects of blended learning on language learning outcomes (Tawil, 2018), there is a need for a more in-depth investigation into the specific impacts of blended learning on students' engagement and participation in classroom-based oral activities. In addition, this issue remains unexplored in the Ethiopian context. The present study aims to fill this research gap by investigating the effects of blended learning on student engagement in classroom oral activities. The findings of this study can contribute to a deeper understanding of the role of blended learning in promoting students' active participation and engagement in language learning, especially in the context of developing oral communication skills. Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate the impact of blended learning on students' engagement in oral activities in the classroom at Hawassa University of Teacher Education.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

As blended learning effectively integrates multiple educational theories to create a dynamic learning environment that fosters student engagement, the current research is based on the theoretical principles of eclectic learning theory. This theory posits that no single method is universally effective; instead, educators should draw from a range of pedagogical frameworks to create a more holistic learning environment (Kumar, 2013). By tailoring instruction to the unique characteristics of learners, eclectic learning promotes a deeper understanding and engagement. In addition, this approach emphasizes flexibility and adaptability in teaching methods, enabling instructors to adjust their strategies based on the context and learner characteristics (Chernus et al., 2022). It maintains a learner-centered focus, encouraging students to take ownership of their education through self-directed and collaborative activities. By utilizing diverse instructional strategies, including direct instruction and experiential learning, it caters to different learning styles and promotes contextual relevance through real-world applications and multimedia tools (Ravi & Karmenivannan, 2024). In blended learning environments, the eclectic learning theory facilitates the combination of online and face-to-face learning, encouraging collaborative efforts and self-regulated learning (Kumar, 2013). By incorporating technology and promoting critical thinking, this theory enhances engagement and prepares students for complex interconnected challenges.

Eclectic learning theory, particularly within the context of blended learning, effectively synthesizes several educational theories and frameworks to enhance students' engagement

and comprehension. For instance, constructivism emphasizes that learners construct knowledge through experiences and interactions that are facilitated in blended environments through both online and face-to-face activities (Bada & Olusegun, 2015). Furthermore, connectivism extends this idea by highlighting the importance of networks and digital tools in learning, positing that knowledge is distributed across a network of connections that learners must navigate (Foroughi, 2015). Self-Regulated Learning focuses on the learner's ability to manage their own Learning process, promoting flexibility in accessing resources at their own pace (Zimmerman, 1990). The community of inquiry framework advocates for a collaborative learning experience in which cognitive, social, and teaching presence interact to foster deep learning; blended learning supports this through online discussions and group projects (Akyol et al., 2009). In addition, transactional distance theory addresses the psychological and communicative space between instructors and learners, with blended learning reducing this distance by combining synchronous and asynchronous elements for immediate feedback (Dron et al., 2004). Finally, multimedia learning theory suggests that (Mayer, 2005) incorporating various media formats can enhance understanding and retention, catering to different learning preferences in blended settings (Rudolph, 2017). By integrating these theories, eclectic learning in blended environments allows for a more personalized, engaging, and operative educational experience that meets the diverse needs of learners in the current digital age.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study conceptualizes Google Classroom and Telegram-based blended instruction as a way to enhance student teachers' engagement in classroom oral activities at Hawassa College of Teacher Education in Ethiopia. The instructional design integrates face-to-face teaching of speaking skills with asynchronous online resources such as video and audio that present oral skills using Google Classroom and Telegram. These videos were projected in the classroom during instruction to facilitate collaborative viewing, discussion, and guided analysis. To extend learning beyond the classroom, the videos were then shared via a dedicated Google Classroom and Telegram group set up by the researchers, so that learners could revisit the content for further individual study, reflection, and practice. Classroom activities are designed to encourage learner interaction, co-creation of meaning, and contextualized application of language skills, which in turn enhances students' engagement. Tasks include debates, describing people and places, group discussions, reflections, and interactive communicative exercises that promote speaking skills for real-life language use. This approach supports the development of students' engagement in classroom oral activities and enhances their speaking skills.

Furthermore, the study uses equal strategies such as offline video access, projector use, and community-based digital resources such as students' smartphones and personal computers to alleviate infrastructure constraints. These steps are intended to guarantee that all students, irrespective of connectivity issues, can gain regular and contextualized exposure to blended speaking skills exercises, which will improve their participation in oral activities in the classroom. The framework aims to close the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world language use by integrating oral skills lessons into multimodal and interactive environments. This will increase learners' engagement and help them communicate more effectively, accurately, and appropriately in a variety of communicative contexts.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Research Design

The researchers used a quasi-experimental design due to the nature of the study. This is mostly because the study investigated the impacts of blended learning on learners' engagement in classroom oral activities; the participants were divided into control and experimental groups. Therefore, the impact of the independent variable (blended learning approach) on the dependent variable (classroom engagement) was examined using two non-equivalent groups.

Research Setting, participants and Sampling Techniques

The research was carried out from October to December 2024 at the government institution of Hawassa College of Teacher Education in Hawassa, Ethiopia. All first-year student teachers enrolled for Communicative English Language Skills II (Enla1012) course in the first semester of the 2024 academic year were the target population of the study. The research setting and participants were chosen using a purposive sampling. The primary reason the researchers chose Hawassa College of Teacher Education for their study was that the college has internet access and offered them access to a fully functional, modern ICT lab with internet connectivity. Two intact sections of first-year students from the Moral Education Department were selected for the study. The participants' degree of technological proficiency, availability, and desire to engage were all taken into account during the selection process. The experimental group with 35 participants and the control group with 31 students were the two groups that were randomly assigned because they were on similar performance level before blended learning intervention.

Data Gathering Tools

The researchers prepared and administered pre-survey and post-survey questionnaires, classroom observations and interview, which were conducted to collect data on students' engagement in classroom oral activities. The questionnaire was adapted from used sources like (Heilporn et al., 2020, Fredricks et al., 2004 and Kahu, 2013). It contains 40 Likert-scale questions to investigate the engagement behavior, 6 questions for blended learning features that contributed to students' engagement and 6 questions of attitudes toward blended learning. The researchers prepared the questionnaire in a Likert scale format with responses such as (5) strongly agree, (4) agree, (3) undecided, (2) disagree, and (1) strongly disagree, with scores of 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively.

In addition, to cross-check the data gathered by using a questionnaire that focused on the students' engagement in oral activities, the researchers used classroom observation and interview to collect qualitative data. The focus of the observation was on the general atmosphere of the classroom and on the participation of a particular student in line with the components of engagement. The researchers used an observation checklist and conducted 12 participatory observations in three consecutive months as of the first week of the intervention by taking field notes among the control and experimental groups while the students were learning the Communicative English Skills course II. Finally, after blended learning interventions, semi structured interview, which contains five questions, was conducted with five randomly selected participants from treatment group to investigate the students' perception toward blended learning.

The Research Procedure

A careful set of protocols was followed by researchers to ensure the validity and success of this investigation. Initially, they prepared instructional materials for control and experimental groups. The blended learning material, which included videos, audio, animation, and interactive oral activities, was adapted from the existing teaching material, which was prepared by Ministry of Education, by following the medium-impact approach. This helped the researchers to use the similar material with different approach (blended learning for treatment group and face-to-face learning for comparison group), and to create comparable classroom instruction among both groups. Next to that the researchers conducted pre-test for both groups at the same time.

Then, before the intervention, the treatment group students participated in a half-day training session arranged by researchers. Training focused on how to register and use Google classroom and telegram for learning course content. Any technical issues with information and communication technology (ICT) that would have prevented the study from being implemented smoothly were resolved by this training. In order for the students in the experimental group to register on the Google Classroom website and in the Telegram group to gain access, the researchers asked them to send their email addresses. Subsequently, the primary investigator established a Google Classroom class and furnished the students with a code to gain entry. Following the pre-test (pre-survey), the instructional intervention started immediately and lasted for 12 weeks, with three sessions per week for the experimental and control groups from October to December 2024. Speaking skills instructions were provided to both groups by the same teacher (the first researcher). In blended learning interventions, the researchers utilized digital tools such as multimedia resources, videos, audio and animations to complement the traditional printed materials and provide a richer learning experience. The researchers encouraged the students' independent and collaborative learning for both groups. Personalization is also essential because diverse assignments according to students' interests and skill levels guarantee that every student remains interested and properly challenged. Collaborative strategies such as group work and online discussion forums also used to encourage peer learning and enhance learning outcomes.

Throughout the intervention phase, the researcher kept an eye on both groups' development and gave the students comments to help them get better at speaking in class and participating. To improve engagement and a variety of speaking skills, the researcher created several tasks that were used throughout the intervention. To accommodate various learning preferences and styles, the tasks included a variety of activities, including role-playing, storytelling, debates, and presentations. Moreover, a range of web, audio, and video resources related to the speaking skills course and activities were made available to the experimental group. However, the control group students performed the same activities only in the face-to-face scenarios. At the end, the post-survey was administered to both groups simultaneously on the same day, precisely one week after the last intervention session. In addition, the researchers distributed the questionnaires to determining specific blended learning feature helped students to be engaged. Finally, the researchers conducted the interview by randomly selecting five participants from experimental group.

Validity and Reliability

The degree to which a study accurately represents or evaluates a certain notion that the researcher is trying to test is known as validity in research (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). As several forms of validity are summarized under the term construct validity, which is a psychological and affective concept that cannot be tested using statistical methods, it was assumed that construct validity can be assessed at different stages of the data collection process. In this regard, prior to data collection, the instruments were reviewed and evaluated

by a doctoral student in English language teaching and two English language experts to confirm the validity of the survey items and intervention materials. These language specialists provided feedback on the questions' structure, as well as the activities' and materials' suitability for the study's aims and objectives. After considering their recommendations and criticisms, the necessary revisions were made to the instrument. A pilot study was then conducted to determine whether the instrument was effective and valid for collecting the intended data. Finally, items reliability was checked by using Cronbach's alpha test. A Cronbach's alpha value of 0.794 indicates that the items of the questionnaire are closely related and consistently measure the construct of engagement, confirming that the questionnaire is a valid instrument for assessing the desired construct.

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted in accordance with the recommendations of the Human Research Ethics Committee of Hawassa University. The study protocol was approved by Hawassa University's College Research Ethics Review Committee (CRERC) with a letter under reference number [CSSH/304/2024], date June 20, 2024. All participants provided oral informed consent after being fully informed of the purpose of the investigation.

Methods of Data Analysis

The collected data were examined using t-test in SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, version 27) to see if there were any statistically significant effects of blended learning on students' involvement in classroom oral activities. The researchers averaged the responses to every engagement question to determine each participant's engagement score by creating composite mean. To determine the early levels of engagement for each group, the pre-survey scores of the two groups were first examined using descriptive statistics. The mean difference between each group's pre- and post-survey ratings was evaluated using a paired-sample t-test. Additionally, an independent sample t-test was used to determine the mean difference between the pre- and post-test scores of the two groups. In addition, the researchers also computed Cohen's d effect size to ascertain the extent of observed differences. The effect size result was interpreted based on (Cohen, 2013) suggestion: small $d = 0.2$, medium $d = 0.5$ and large $d = 0.8$. The researchers conducted a thematic analysis for the observation data. To determine the blended learning feature that had a greater impact on students' engagement in classroom oral activities, the researchers used a multiple linear regression model by checking the assumptions like linearity, independence, normality, homoscedasticity and multicollinearity. Finally, thematic analysis was used for the observation and interview data to determine the respondents' perception toward blended learning.

RESULT

In this segment, the researchers presented data and discussed the finding of the study under each specific research question.

Level of Students' Engagement In Classroom Oral Activities In Blended Learning Environments Compared to Conventional Learning

Quantitative Analysis

Table 1. Independent Samples t-test Result of Students' Pre-survey

Pre-survey Result of both control and treatment group	t-test for Equality of Means						
	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
	.222	64	.825	.01182	.05325	-.09457	.11821

Table 3 provides an independent sample test of the students' pre-survey results. According to the information provided in the table, the p-value (Sig. 2-tailed) is 0.825. Because the p-value (0.825) is greater than the significance level of 0.05, researchers can conclude that the difference in the mean of the pre-survey test scores between the control and treatment groups is not statistically significant. This finding is important because it suggests that the two groups were well matched in terms of their baseline performance on the pretest.

Table 5. Independent Samples Test Result of Post-survey

Post-intervention survey	t-test for Equality of Means						
	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Affective engagement	-13.362	64	.000	-1.01189	.07573	-1.1631	-.8606
Behavioral engagement	-12.830	64	.000	-1.09106	.08504	-1.2609	-.9211
Cognitive engagement	-20.267	64	.000	-1.14286	.05639	-1.2555	-1.030
Social engagement	-11.959	64	.000	-.93963	.07857	-1.0966	-.7826
Total post-survey result	-20.298	64	.000	-1.04636	.05155	-1.15	-.9434

As indicated in Table 5, the results from the independent samples t-test on post-survey data revealed significant difference in level of student participation in oral activities in blended learning environments compared to conventional learning settings regarding various dimensions of engagement. All p-values reported were 0.000, indicating strong statistical significance across all components of engagement: affective, behavioral, cognitive, and social. This suggests that there were clear differences in the mean values between the two groups. The results showed a statistically significant difference in the mean scores of students' engagement in oral activities between the control and treatment groups ($p < 0.001$). Therefore, the results suggested that the blended learning intervention had a statistically significant effect on students' engagement in oral activities. The blended learning group demonstrated significantly higher engagement than the conventional group.

Table 6. Paired samples test result

	Paired Differences					T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Control group	-.08468	.20632	.03706	-.16036	-.00900	-2.285	30	.030
Experimental group	-.14286	.30622	.05176	-.24805	-1.03767	-22.08	34	.000

Based on the paired sample test results provided in Table 6, the mean difference between the control group's pre- and post-survey results is -0.08468, with a statistically significant p-value of 0.030 ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that the control group, which did not receive the blended learning intervention, experienced a small but statistically significant increase in engagement in classroom oral activities from the pre-survey to the post-survey. The mean difference between the experimental group's pre- and post-survey results was -1.14286, with a highly statistically significant p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.001$). This indicates that the blended learning group experienced a substantial and statistically significant increase in their engagement in classroom oral activities from pre-survey to post-survey.

Qualitative Analysis from Classroom Observations

The researchers observed both experimental and control groups of students during their Communicative English classes. The observations concentrated on many facets of involvement, including social, behavioral, affective, and cognitive engagement. The checklist was utilized by the researchers to document students' engagement behavior. When comparing the treatment and control groups, the observation results demonstrated notable changes in the treatment groups' classroom engagement behaviors.

The results highlight the significant improvements in affective engagement behaviors observed in the treatment group compared to the control group. Emotional engagement is reflected in students' growing enthusiasm and confidence in the classroom. The enhancement in participation during group discussions indicates that students are not only willing to express their ideas, but are also becoming more invested in their peers' contributions. In addition, compared to the control group, the observation result highlights a significant improvement in the behavioral engagement of the treatment group. Observations show that a significant number of students attend classes regularly, indicating commitment to their education. Additionally, active participation during lessons has improved, with more students volunteering to contribute to discussions and engage in class work. Cognitive engagement has also seen notable improvements, particularly in students' abilities to ask and answer questions. When compared with the control group, the increased frequency of questioning in the experimental group suggests a deeper engagement with the content, as students seek to clarify their understanding. Furthermore, experimental group students actively participated in problem-solving activities, applied critical thinking skills, and utilized concepts learned in class. The use of metacognitive strategies was also observed, with students reflecting on their learning processes and demonstrating enhanced self-regulation.

Social engagement can be manifested through collaboration among students, participation in pair and group discussions, and communication and effective collaboration. This collaborative spirit not only aids in the sharing of ideas, but also helps to build a sense of community within the classroom, where students learn from one another and develop essential teamwork skills. Thus, the observations indicate that most students showed significant improvement in the behavioral, cognitive, emotional and social engagements. This multifaceted growth highlights a positive trend in the classroom, fostering a dynamic and interactive learning environment.

Effect Size

Table 7. The result of Effect Sizes

		Standardizera	Point Estimate	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower	Upper
Post-survey result	Cohen's d	.20902	-5.006	-5.992	-4.010
	Hedges' correction	.21151	-4.947	-5.921	-3.963
	Glass's delta	.22664	-4.617	-5.805	-3.416

The Effect size results offer additional insights into the magnitude and practical significance of the effects of blended learning in enhancing students' classroom engagement (see Table 7). Cohen's d value of -5.006 suggests a very large effect size, indicating that the blended learning group's post-survey scores were, on average, 5.006 standard deviations higher than the control group's post-survey scores. Thus, the effect size measure provides compelling evidence that the blended learning approach had a substantial and positive impact on enhancing students' classroom engagement, as reflected in their significantly higher post-survey performance than the control group.

Blended Learning Features Most Significantly Impact Learners' Engagement in Classroom Oral Activities

Identifying the specific blended learning features that helped students enhance their engagement in classroom speaking activities was another significant research question in this study. Data were analyzed using multiple linear regression models, as follows:

Table 10. Regression Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.793	.120		14.927	.000
	Collaboration	.087	.030	.166	2.914	.007
	Multimedia resources and interactive speaking exercises	.102	.040	.262	2.579	.015
	Flexibility and personalization	.104	.037	.263	2.795	.009
	Face-to-face Learning	.016	.043	.039	.372	.712
	Assessment	.059	.030	.143	1.997	.056
	Real-time feedbacks	.083	.027	.249	3.035	.005

a. Dependent Variable: Engagement

The formula for a multiple linear regression can be expressed as $Y = 1.793 + .166 \times \text{Collaboration} + .262 \times \text{Multimedia Resources and Interactive Speaking Exercises} + .263 \times \text{Flexibility and personalization} + .039 \times \text{Face-to-face Learning} + .143 \times \text{Assessment} + .249 \times \text{Real-time Feedback}$. The analysis of multiple linear regressions presented in Table 10 illustrates how different blended learning features affect student engagement. The standardized beta coefficients from the regression model enabled a comparison of the relative influence of each predictor variable, with higher beta values indicating a stronger contribution. Especially, the variable "collaborative learning" demonstrates a positive and significant correlation with engagement scores, shown by a beta coefficient of (.166) and a significant value of ($p = .007$). This implies that increased collaboration in the learning environment is linked to improved engagement in oral classroom activities.

The other variables that contributed the most to improving students' classroom engagement were: "Multimedia Resource (video, audio) and interactive speaking exercises" (Beta = .262,

$p = .015$); "Flexibility and personalization" (Beta =.263, $p = .009$); and "Real-time Feedback" (Beta =.249, $p = .005$). The "assessment" variable was not significant for a little bit, having a beta coefficient of 1.997 ($p = 0.056$) in the analysis, indicating that although conventional classroom interactions may aid in the development of students' engagement, their influence is not as strong in this model as that of the other variables. The final variable, "face-to-face learning," had a beta value of.039 ($p = .712$), which was positive but not statistically significant. This indicates that it did not have a significant impact on enhancing students' engagement in oral classroom activities.

PARTICIPANTS PERCEPTION TOWARDS BLENDED LEARNING

Table 11. Results of the Students' Attitude toward Blended Learning

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
I enjoy the flexibility of being able to learn at my own pace in a blended learning environment.	35	4.2286	.64561
I have found the combination of face-to-face and online learning activities more effective for my learning.	35	4.1714	.66358
I believe that blended learning helps me to be more engaged and motivated in my studies.	35	4.1143	.58266
I feel that the online components of blended learning courses are well integrated with the face-to-face activities.	35	4.2286	.68966
I find the technology used in blended learning courses to be easy to use and accessible.	35	4.1143	.63113
I have a positive attitude toward blended learning.	35	4.1429	.60112
Valid N (listwise)	35		

Table 11 presents the results of the participants' attitudes towards blended learning. Based on the statistics provided, the students reflected a positive attitude towards blended learning. The high mean score ($M=4.23$) and relatively low standard deviation (0.65) of the first question in Table 11 indicate that students strongly valued the flexibility and self-paced nature of the blended learning approach. In addition, students' positive perception of the combined face-to-face and online learning activities ($M = 4.17$, $SD = 0.66$) suggests that they believe that the blended format is effective for their learning. In addition, students' agreement that blended learning enhances their engagement and motivation ($M = 4.11$, $SD = 0.58$) is an important outcome. Increased engagement and motivation are often associated with improved learning outcomes, especially language acquisition (Kintu et al., 2017). Furthermore, the students' positive perception of the integration between online and face-to-face components ($M = 4.23$, $SD = 0.69$) indicated that the blended learning design was well-structured and coherent. Finally, the students' judgment of the technology used in blended learning courses as easy to use and accessible ($M = 4.11$, $SD = 0.63$) suggests that the technological infrastructure and support are adequate. Overall, the students had a positive attitude toward blended learning ($M = 4.14$, $SD = 0.60$). The relatively low standard deviations (all below 0.70) suggest that the students' responses were quite consistent, indicating a general consensus among the participants regarding their positive attitudes toward effectiveness of blended learning for improving their engagement in classroom oral activities. The following interview result also supports this finding.

The Result of Interview

In a present interview discussion, participants expressed their insights on blended learning, emphasizing both its general use and the improvement of their engagement in classroom oral activities. Their experiences are explored in this thematic analysis, which also highlights key themes that came up in the interviews.

General perception of blended learning: Participants expressed a positive attitude towards blended learning, emphasizing its various benefits and their personal experiences with the approach. All respondents highlighted the freedom and individualization that blended learning offers, allowing them to access resources and learn at their own pace. For instance, R1, "I truly value the freedom it provides... to access online resources." While the advantages of online learning were evident, some participants mentioned limitations in their interactions with peers and lecturers, primarily due to internet connectivity issues.

Flexibility as an important plea: Flexibility emerged as a central theme in the discussions surrounding blended learning. Respondents valued the ability to manage their time effectively, allowing them to balance their studies with other commitments. R3, "I feel like I have the best of both blended learning and face-to-face learning," underscoring the benefits of being able to navigate their educational responsibilities. Additionally, the ubiquitous nature of blended learning enables students to engage with content anytime and anywhere, contributing to a more individualized and personalized educational experience.

Perceived helpfulness in enhancing engagement: The participants acknowledged the effectiveness of blended learning in enhancing engagement within the classroom oral activities. Most respondents felt that the integration of online and face-to-face elements created a more dynamic learning environment. R2 noted, "The combination... keeps things dynamic and interesting," reflecting a shared feeling among respondents. Additionally, blended learning was seen as a motivating factor that enhanced participants' confidence in engaging in oral activities. As R5 mentioned, "This side of blended learning helped me to participate in the classroom," illustrating how the approach encourages active involvement in the learning process.

Challenges faced in blended learning: Despite recognizing the benefits, participants also identified several challenges related with blended learning. Technical issues, particularly related to internet access and device functionality, were common concerns. R4 expressed, "I find some aspects of blended learning challenging... my device... is not well functioning." Furthermore, R 2 and 3 replied that they face challenges of internet access at home. In addition, R 5 said, "As it is a new approach, it took time to familiarize myself with the online setting. These challenges highlight the need for additional support and resources to help students adapt effectively to blended learning environments.

Future Preferences for Blended Learning: Looking to the future, all respondents expressed a strong desire to continue with blended learning. They appreciated the balance it offers between online and in-person interactions, noting that this combination keeps them engaged and motivated. For instance, R1 reacted, "... I would prefer to continue with blended learning. I enjoy the mix of online and in-person interactions. The online components let me explore topics more deeply, while the face-to-face classes provide valuable discussions and connections with my classmates and teachers. This combination keeps me engaged and motivated." The participants felt that blended learning not only makes the learning process more versatile but also encourages students to take an active role in their learning process. They would prefer to continue with blended learning in the future, as it offers the advantage of balancing studies with other commitments and enhancing their learning experience.

DISCUSSIONS

The results of the pre-survey ($t(64) = .222, p = .825$) indicate that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean pre-survey scores of the two groups being compared because the t-statistic is very small and the p-value is much larger than .05. In addition, the results indicated that the two groups had comparable baseline levels of classroom engagement before the intervention. This similarity suggests that any observed differences in post-survey scores or other outcome measures are more likely to be a direct result of the blended learning intervention than pre-existing variations between the groups.

To evaluate post-intervention changes, the researchers used the independent sample t-test and the paired sample t-test. The results in Table 5 show that the t-statistic ($t(64) = -20.298, P = .000$) is large and negative, and the p-value is extremely small (less than .001). This indicates that there was a significant difference between the mean post-survey scores of the two groups. In addition, the paired-sample t-test results in Tables 8 and 9 show similar findings. The results show that blended learning helped enhance student engagement in the experimental group compared to the control group. Furthermore, the observation results showed that the blended learning intervention had a positive impact on the experimental group's classroom engagement compared to the control group's conventional instruction. In addition, the result of the effect size analysis in Table 7, using Cohen's d, revealed a very large and statistically significant positive effect of blended learning on student engagement. These results are consistent with earlier research showing how blended learning can improve student engagement and learning outcomes (Shenkut et al., 2022). This suggests that the blended learning approach was effective in enhancing various dimensions of student engagement, including affective, behavioral, and cognitive engagement.

The second research question is related to the specific blended learning features that help students enhance their classroom engagement. In relation to this, the regression analysis results have identified some aspects of blended learning that have a major impact on students' engagement in classroom oral activities (see Table 10). Multimedia resources, collaborative learning, flexibility, and personalization were powerful predictors. Multimedia resources encompass a variety of content formats that integrate many media formats to communicate information and improve educational opportunities. Images, animations, audio, and video are examples of these materials. The results showed that students' participation in oral activities was significantly improved by multimedia resources ($B = 2.928, p = .005$). This is in line with previous study by (Qizi & Ugli, 2021), who highlighted the benefits of multimedia materials. In addition, the analysis revealed that collaborative learning ($B = 3.177, p = .001$) was another critical factor that emerged from the analysis. Collaborative tasks encourage students to practice speaking in a supportive environment, which can significantly enhance their confidence and proficiency and lead to strong classroom engagement.

Flexibility and personalization are two crucial concepts in education that enhance the learning experience by addressing individual needs and preferences. Flexibility and personalization ($B = 2.900, p = .010$) were hallmarks of blended learning that promoted engagement. Flexible and personalized learning experiences allow students to progress at their own pace and choose resources that resonate with their interests, leading to greater engagement in oral activities. This finding is consistent with that of (Bekele Sime et al., 2024), which indicates that personalized approaches can lead to enhanced language performance. Furthermore, regression analysis revealed that assessment ($B = 0.217, p = .857$) and face-to-face learning ($B = 0.417, p = .712$) did not significantly affect students' engagement in classroom oral activities. The lack of a significant impact from face-to-face learning indicates that reliance

solely on conventional classroom settings might not meet the diverse needs of all learners, particularly in developing students' engagement in classroom.

The results of this analysis underscore the importance of incorporating blended learning components that effectively enhance students' engagement and speaking performance. Educators can create a more dynamic and responsive learning environment by integrating multimedia resources, facilitating collaborative learning opportunities, and allowing for flexibility and personalization. These strategies not only align with the eclectic paradigm's emphasis on diverse methodologies but also address the varying needs of learners in language instruction. These findings emphasize the need to move away from face-to-face learning models towards more innovative and interactive approaches. This shift can lead to improved student engagement and performance in oral language activities, ultimately fostering a more effective language-learning experience.

Finally, the researchers assessed participants' attitudes toward blended learning. The results presented in Table 11 reveal that students had a positive attitude toward blended learning. Thus, the results highlight students' appreciation for the flexibility, effectiveness, engagement, integration, and ease of use of the blended learning approach. Moreover, the result of interview supports the above finding. Researchers interviewed participants about their perception of blended learning, which they found positive due to its flexibility, access to online resources, and combination of face-to-face and online methods. They appreciated the flexibility, but some students faced challenges like time management and home internet access. The participants confirmed that blended learning improved their engagement in classroom oral activities by combining online and in-person elements. Finally, they expressed that, as it has greater impact on their learning experience they would prefer to continue with blended learning in the future. This aligns with the literature, which suggests that the flexibility of blended learning can accommodate diverse learner needs and preferences, leading to improved student satisfaction and engagement (Kintu et al., 2017). These results provide significant insights into the design and implementation of blended learning programs for English language education.

Thus, it is important to note that blended learning has become a revolutionary strategy in the twenty-first century, addressing the issues caused by the digital divide and aligning it with various learning theories. In addition, using eclectic learning theory, which integrates multiple educational frameworks, language instruction is essential for improving students' educational experience. This theory lays the groundwork for student-centered and active learning approaches, which have been shown to improve students' engagement in oral activities in the classroom because it asserts that no single approach is always successful and that teachers should use a variety of pedagogical frameworks to create a more comprehensive learning environment (Kumar, 2013). This is also notable because it highlights disparities in access to various resources, including digital resources and technology. Hence, when digital literacy is adequately supported by technology access, blended learning can improve student engagement and learning outcomes.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the effects of blended learning on student engagement in classroom oral activities among first-year moral education students at Hawassa College of Teacher Education. The findings indicate that blended learning significantly improved student engagement (behavioral, cognitive, affective, and social dimensions) compared to conventional methods. Students expressed positive attitudes towards blended learning, appreciating its flexibility and effectiveness. These findings suggest that blended learning can address diverse learning needs and promote collaborative environments. The study recommends that educators, especially in English language teaching, adopt blended learning

strategies and utilize tools like Google Classroom and Telegram. Additionally, institutions should invest in reliable Internet access; provide students with digital resources for effective technology integration in the classroom.

Finally, there are certain limitations to this study that should be considered by future researchers when investigating related subjects. For instance, it was carried out with a small sample size, which might not be representative of the broader population. This allows other researchers to challenge the findings using a bigger and more varied sample. Moreover, a longer time frame may be advantageous for future research to have a more thorough understanding, as the 12-week study period may not adequately reflect the long-term consequences of blended learning. The results of this study may be disproved by bigger sample sizes in future studies that employ more complex statistical techniques, such as ANCOVA, to account for confounding variables. By resolving these limitations, future research can look more closely at how blended learning affects students' engagement in classroom oral activities.

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